

Reactive Methylene Compounds. Part VIII. Condensations with Benzenediazonium Salts

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Benzenediazonium salts have been condensed with diethyl malonate, 1-carbamoyl-3-methyl-5-pyrazolone, indan-1,3-dione, and methone. Characteristics of the products obtained have been described.

The work on the condensation of reactive methylene compounds with benzenediazonium salts has been extended (Garg and Joshi, this *Journal*, 1960, 37, 626; Garg, *ibid.*, 1961, 38, 113, 115); the coupling of diethyl malonate, 1-carbamoyl-3-methyl-5-pyrazolone, indan-1,3-dione, and methone with some phenyldiazonium salts has been described in this paper.

It has been observed that 1-carbamoyl-3-methyl-4-(substituted benzeneazo)-5-pyrazolones (II) lose carbamoyl group, when heated in alcohol, forming 3-methyl-4-(substituted benzeneazo)-5-pyrazolones (III).

EXPERIMENTAL**

Diethyl malonate was commercially available. 1-Carbamoyl-3-methyl-5-pyrazolone was prepared by cyclization of semicarbazone of ethyl acetoacetate in presence of ammonia. The latter was obtained from ethyl acetoacetate and semicarbazide. Indan-1,3-dione (Teeters and Shriner, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 55, 3027) and methone (Vorländer, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1929, 77, 245) were prepared by known methods.

Condensation of Benzenediazonium Salts with Reactive Methylene Compounds.—The benzenediazonium salts were condensed with diethyl malonate, 1-carbamoyl-3-methyl-5-pyrazolone, indan-1,3-dione, and methone in the same manner, as described in earlier communications (Garg and Joshi, *loc. cit.*). Characteristics of the various compounds obtained are reported in Tables I and II.

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** Melting points are uncorrected.

TABLE I

No.	Benzeneazo derivative formed.	Diethyl malonate		1-Carbamoyl-3-methyl-5-pyrazolone.									
		%Yield.	M.P.	Colour.	Formula.	Found.	Calc.	%Yield.	M.P.	Colour.	Formula.	Found.	Calc.
1.	4-Methoxy-	-	-	-	-	-	-	86	201°	Red	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₃	N:25.68%	25.45%
2.	2-Chloro-	79	73°	Pale yellow	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ O ₄ N ₃ Cl	Cl: 11.69%	11.69%	91	210°	Yellow	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₃ Cl	Cl:12.38	12.70
3.	3-Chloro-	-	-	-	-	-	-	92	208°	Do	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₃ Cl	Cl:12.29	12.70
4.	4-Chloro-	-	-	-	-	-	-	93	205°	Do	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₃ Cl	Cl:12.41	12.70
5.	4-Nitro-	83	78°	Pale yellow	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ O ₆ N ₃	N: 13.31	13.59	94	266°	Golden yellow	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₄ N ₆	N:28.68	28.96
6.	3-Nitro-	79	88°	Yellow	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ O ₆ N ₃	N: 13.28	13.59	92	211°	Yellow	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₄ N ₆	N:28.71	28.96
7.	4-Methyl-	78	71°	Do	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₃	N: 9.92	10.07	86	192°	Do	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₃	N:29.88	27.02
8.	2-Chloro-4-nitro-	79	95°	Chocolate	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ O ₆ N ₃ Cl	Cl: 10.12	10.33	92	201°	Dark brown	C ₁₁ H ₉ O ₄ N ₆ Cl	Cl:10.71	10.93
9.	2-Nitro-4-chloro-	81	96°	Red	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ O ₆ N ₃ Cl	Cl: 10.01	10.33	90	244°	Yellow	C ₁₁ H ₉ O ₄ N ₆ Cl	Cl:10.83	10.93

TABLE II

No.	%Yield.	M.P.	Colour.	Indan-1,3-dione.		M.P.	Colour.	Formula.	Found.	Calc.	%Yield.	M.P.	Colour.	Formula.	Found.	Calc.
				Formula.	Found.											
1.	88	170°	Orange-red	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₂	N: 9.97%	-	-	-	10.00%	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
2.	92	234°	Dirty yellow	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	Cl: 12.41	12.47	92	1240	Golden yellow	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	Cl:12.48%	12.75%	12.75%			
3.	92	178°	Do	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	Cl: 12.27	12.47	93	1220	Light orange	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	Cl:12.61	12.75	12.75			
4.	92	235°	Violet	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	Cl: 12.41	12.47	93	210°	Pale yellow	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	Cl:12.61	12.75	12.75			
5.	95	280°	Yellow	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₄ N ₃	N: 14.02	14.23	90	216°	Yellow	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ O ₄ N ₃	N:14.59	14.53	14.53			
6.	93	296°	Brownish yellow	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₄ N ₃	N: 13.98	14.23	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
7.	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
8.	92	238°	Dirty yellow	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₄ N ₃ Cl	Cl: 0.61	10.77	93	178°	Brown	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ O ₄ N ₃ Cl	Cl:10.68	10.9	10.9			
9.	92	239°	Red	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₄ N ₃ Cl	Cl: 10.58	10.77	93	165°	Brown	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ O ₄ N ₃ Cl	Cl:10.72	10.97	10.97			

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